

D - Form of SMARANDACHE GROUPOID

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Abstract :

The set of p different equivalence classes is $\mathbb{Z}_p = \{ [0], [1], [2], \dots, [k] \dots [p-1] \}$. For convenience, we have omitted the brackets and written k in place of $[k]$. Thus

$$\mathbb{Z}_p = \{ 0, 1, 2, \dots, k \dots p-1 \}$$

The elements of $\mathbb{Z}_p$ can be written uniquely as m -adic numbers. If $r = (a_{n-1} a_{n-2} \dots a_1 a_0)_m$ and $s = (b_{n-1} b_{n-2} \dots b_1 b_0)_m$ be any two elements of $\mathbb{Z}_p$, then $r \Delta s$ is defined as $(|a_{n-1} - b_{n-1}| |a_{n-2} - b_{n-2}| \dots |a_1 - b_1| |a_0 - b_0|)_m$ then $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$ is a groupoid known as SMARANDACHE GROUPOID. If we define a binary relation $r \equiv s \Leftrightarrow r \Delta C(r) = s \Delta C(s)$, where $C(r)$ and $C(s)$ are the complements of r and s respectively, then we see that this relation is equivalence relation and partitions $\mathbb{Z}_p$ into some equivalence classes. The equivalence class

$D_{\text{sup}(\mathbb{Z}_p)} = \{ r \in \mathbb{Z}_p : r \Delta C(r) = \text{Sup}(\mathbb{Z}_p) \}$ is defined as D -form. Properties of SMARANDACHE GROUPOID and D -form are discussed here.

Key Words : SMARANDACHE GROUPOID, complement element and D -form.

1. Introduction :

Let m be a positive integer greater than one. Then every positive integer r can be written uniquely in the form $r = a_{n-1} m^{n-1} + a_{n-2} m^{n-2} + \dots + a_1 m + a_0$ where $n \geq 0$, a_i is an integer, $0 \leq a_i < m$, m is called the base of r , which is denoted by $(a_{n-1} a_{n-2} \dots a_1 a_0)_m$. The absolute difference of two integers $r = (a_{n-1} a_{n-2} \dots a_1 a_0)_m$ and $s = (b_{n-1} b_{n-2} \dots b_1 b_0)_m$ denoted by $r \Delta s$ and defined as

$$\begin{aligned} r \Delta s &= (|a_{n-1} - b_{n-1}| |a_{n-2} - b_{n-2}| \dots |a_1 - b_1| |a_0 - b_0|)_m \\ &= (c_{n-1} c_{n-2} \dots c_1 c_0)_m, \text{ where } c_i = |a_i - b_i| \text{ for } i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1. \end{aligned}$$

In this operation, $r \Delta s$ is not necessarily equal to $|r - s|$ i.e. absolute difference of r and s .

If the equivalence classes of $\mathbb{Z}_p$ are expressed as m -adic numbers, then $\mathbb{Z}_p$ with binary operation Δ is a groupoid, which contains some non-trivial groups. This groupoid is defined as SMARANDACHE GROUPOID. Some properties of this groupoid are established here.

2. Preliminaries :

We recall the following definitions and properties to introduce SMARANDACHE GROUPOID.

Definition 2.1 (2)

Let p be a fixed integer greater than one. If a and b are integers such that $a-b$ is divisible by p , then a is congruent to b modulo p and indicate this by writing $a \equiv b \pmod{p}$. This congruence relation is an equivalence relation on the set of all integers.

The set of p different equivalence classes is $\mathbb{Z}_p = \{ 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, p-1 \}$

Proposition 2.2 (1)

If $a \equiv b \pmod{p}$ and $c \equiv d \pmod{p}$

- Then
- i) $a +_p c = b +_p d$
 - ii) $a \times_p c = b \times_p d$

Proposition 2.3 (2)

Let m be a positive integer greater than one. Then every integer r can be written uniquely in the form

$$r = a_{n-1}m^{n-1} + a_{n-2}m^{n-2} + \dots + a_1m + a_0$$

$$= \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} a_i m^i \quad \text{for } i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1 ;$$

Where $n \geq 0$, a_i is an integer $0 \leq a_i < m$. Here m is called the base of r , which is denoted by $(a_{n-1}a_{n-2} \dots a_1a_0)_m$.

Proposition 2.4

If $r = (a_{n-1}a_{n-2} \dots a_1a_0)_m$ and $s = (b_{n-1}b_{n-2} \dots b_1b_0)_m$, then

- i) $r = s$ if and only if $a_i = b_i$ for $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1$.
- ii) $r < s$ if and only if $(a_{n-1}a_{n-2} \dots a_1a_0)_m < (b_{n-1}b_{n-2} \dots b_1b_0)_m$
- iii) $r > s$ if and only if $(a_{n-1}a_{n-2} \dots a_1a_0)_m > (b_{n-1}b_{n-2} \dots b_1b_0)_m$

3. Smarandache groupoid :

Definition 3.1

Let $r = (a_{n-1}a_{n-2} \dots a_1 \dots a_1a_0)_m$ and $s = (b_{n-1}b_{n-2} \dots b_i \dots b_1b_0)_m$, then the absolute difference denoted by Δ of r and s is defined as

$$r \Delta s = (c_{n-1}c_{n-2} \dots c_i \dots c_1c_0)_m, \quad \text{where } c_i = |a_i - b_i| \quad \text{for } i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1.$$

Here, $r \Delta s$ is not necessarily equal to $|r - s|$. For example

$$5 = (101)_2 \quad \text{and} \quad 6 = (110)_2 \quad \text{and} \quad 5 \Delta 6 = (011)_2 = 3 \quad \text{but} \quad |5 - 6| = 1.$$

In this paper, we shall consider $5 \Delta 6 = 3$, not $5 \Delta 6 = 1$.

Definition 3.2

Let $(\mathbb{Z}_p, +_p)$ be a commutative group of order $p = m^n$. If the elements of $\mathbb{Z}_p$ are

expressed as m - adic numbers as shown below :

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 &= (00 \dots \dots 00)_m \\
 1 &= (00 \dots \dots 01)_m \\
 2 &= (00 \dots \dots 02)_m \\
 &\dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \\
 m-1 &= (00 \dots \dots 0 \ m-1)_m \\
 m &= (00 \dots \dots 1 \ 0)_m \\
 m+1 &= (00 \dots \dots 1 \ 1)_m \\
 &\dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \\
 m^2-1 &= (00 \dots \dots m-1 \ m-1)_m \\
 m^2 &= (00 \dots \dots 1 \ 0 \ 0)_m \\
 &\dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \\
 m^n-1 &= (m-1 \ m-1 \ \dots \ \dots \ m-1 \ m-1)_m
 \end{aligned}$$

The set $\mathbf{Z}_p$ is closed under binary operation Δ . Thus $(\mathbf{Z}_p, \Delta)$ is a groupoid. The elements $(00 \dots \dots 00)_m$ and $(m-1 \ m-1 \ \dots \ \dots \ m-1 \ m-1)_m$ are called infimum and supremum of $\mathbf{Z}_p$.

The set H_1 of the elements noted below :

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 &= (00 \dots \dots 00)_m \\
 1 &= (00 \dots \dots 01)_m \\
 m &= (00 \dots \dots 1 \ 0)_m \\
 m+1 &= (00 \dots \dots 1 \ 1)_m \\
 &\dots \dots \dots \dots \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{m^{n-1} - m}{m-1} = (0 \ 1 \ \dots \ \dots \ 1 \ 0)_m = \alpha \text{ (say)}$$

$$\frac{m^{n-1} - 1}{m-1} = (0 \ 1 \ \dots \ \dots \ 1 \ 1)_m = \beta \text{ (say)}$$

$$\frac{m^n - m}{m-1} = (1 \ 1 \ \dots \ \dots \ 1 \ 0)_m = \gamma \text{ (say)}$$

$$\frac{m^n - 1}{m-1} = (1 \ 1 \ \dots \ \dots \ 1 \ 1)_m = \delta \text{ (say)}$$

is a proper subset of $\mathbf{Z}_p$.

(H_1, Δ) is a group of order 2^n and its group table is as follows :

Δ	0	1	m	m+1	...	...	α	β	γ	δ
0	0	1	m	m+1	...	...	α	β	γ	δ
1	1	0	m+1	m	...	...	β	α	δ	γ
m	m	m+1	0	1	...	...	γ	δ	α	β
m+1	m+1	m	1	0	...	...	δ	γ	β	α
....										
....										
α	α	β	γ	δ	...	...	0	1	m	m+1
β	β	α	δ	γ	...	...	1	0	m+1	m
γ	γ	δ	α	β	...	...	m	m+1	0	1
δ	δ	γ	β	α	...	...	m+1	m	1	0

Table - 1

Similarly the proper sub-sets

$$H_2 = \{ 0, 2, 2m, 2(m+1) \dots \dots 2\alpha, 2\beta, 2\gamma, 2\delta \}$$

$$H_3 = \{ 0, 3, 3m, 3(m+1) \dots \dots 3\alpha, 3\beta, 3\gamma, 3\delta \}$$

.... ..

$$H_{m-1} = \{ 0, m-1, m(m-1), m^2-1 \dots \dots (m-1)\alpha, (m-1)\beta, (m-1)\gamma, (m-1)\delta \}$$

are groups of order 2^n under the operation absolute difference. So the groupoid (Z_p, Δ) contains mainly the groups (H_1, Δ) , (H_2, Δ) , (H_3, Δ) (H_{m-1}, Δ) and this groupoid is defined as SMARANDACHE GROUPOID . Here we use S.Gd. in place of SMARANDACHE GROUPOID.

Remarks 3.2

i) Let $(Z_p, +p)$ be a commutative group of order p , where $m^{n-1} < p < m^n$, then (Z_p, Δ) is not groupoid.

For example $(Z_5, +5)$ is a commutative group of order 5, where $2^2 < p < 2^3$.

Here $Z_5 = \{ 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 \}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= (000)_2 & 4 &= (100)_2 \\ 1 &= (001)_2 & 5 &= (101)_2 \\ 2 &= (010)_2 & 6 &= (110)_2 \\ 3 &= (011)_2 & 7 &= (111)_2 \end{aligned}$$

A composition table of $\mathbb{Z}_5$ is given below :

Δ	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	1	0	3	2	5
2	2	3	0	1	6
3	3	2	1	0	7
4	4	5	6	7	0

Table - 2

Hence $\mathbb{Z}_5$ is not closed under the operation Δ , i.e. $(\mathbb{Z}_5, \Delta)$ is not a groupoid.

ii) S. Gd. is not necessarily associative.

$$\text{Let } 1 = (00 \dots \dots 01)_m$$

$$2 = (00 \dots \dots 02)_m \text{ and}$$

$$3 = (00 \dots \dots 03)_m \text{ be three elements of } (\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta), \text{ then}$$

$$(1 \Delta 2) \Delta 3 = 2 \text{ and}$$

$$1 \Delta (2 \Delta 3) = 0$$

$$\text{i.e. } (1 \Delta 2) \Delta 3 \neq 1 \Delta (2 \Delta 3).$$

iii) S. Gd. is commutative.

$$\text{iv) S. Gd. has identity element } 0 = (00 \dots \dots 0)_m$$

$$\text{v) Each element of S. Gd. is self inverse i.e. } \forall p \in \mathbb{Z}_p, p \Delta p = 0.$$

Proposition 3.3

If (H, Δ) and (K, Δ) be two groups of order 2^n contained in S. Gd. $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$, then H is isomorphic to K.

Proof is obvious.

4. Complement element in S. Gd. $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$.

Definition 4.1

Let $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$ be a S. Gd., then the complement of any element $p \in \mathbb{Z}_p$ is equal to $p \Delta \text{Sup}(\mathbb{Z}_p) = p \Delta m^{n-1}$ i.e. $C(p) = m^{n-1} \Delta p$. This function is known as complement function and it satisfies the following properties.

$$\text{i) } C(0) = m^n - 1$$

$$\text{ii) } C(m^n - 1) = 0$$

$$\text{ii) } C(C(p)) = p \quad \forall p \in \mathbb{Z}_p$$

$$\text{iv) If } p \leq q \text{ then } C(p) \geq C(q).$$

Definition 4.2

An element p of a S. Gd. $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$ is said to be self complement if $p \Delta \text{sup}(\mathbb{Z}_p) = p$ i.e. $C(p) = p$.

If m is an odd integer greater than one, then $\frac{m^n - 1}{2}$ is the self complement of $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$.

If m is an even integer, then there exists no self complement in $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$.

Remarks 4.3

- i) The complement of an element belonging to a S. Gd. is unique.
- ii) The S. Gd. is closed under complement operation.

5. A binary relation in S. Gd.

Definition 5.1

Let $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$ be a S. Gd. An element p of $\mathbb{Z}_p$ is said to be related to $q \in \mathbb{Z}_p$ iff $p \Delta C(p) = q \Delta C(q)$ and written as $p \equiv q \Leftrightarrow p \Delta C(p) = q \Delta C(q)$.

Proposition 5.2

For the elements p and q of S. Gd. $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$, $p \equiv q \Leftrightarrow C(p) \equiv C(q)$.

Proof: By definition

$$\begin{aligned} p \equiv q &\Leftrightarrow p \Delta C(p) = q \Delta C(q). \\ &\Leftrightarrow C(p) \Delta p = C(q) \Delta q \\ &\Leftrightarrow C(p) \Delta C(C(p)) = C(q) \Delta C(C(q)) \\ &\Leftrightarrow C(p) \equiv C(q) \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 5.3

Let $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$ be a S. Gd., then a binary relation $p \equiv q \Leftrightarrow p \Delta C(p) = q \Delta C(q)$ for $p, q \in \mathbb{Z}_p$, is an equivalence relation.

Proof: Let $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$ be a S. Gd. and for any two elements p and q of $\mathbb{Z}_p$,

let us define a binary relation $p \equiv q \Leftrightarrow p \Delta C(p) = q \Delta C(q)$.

This relation is

i) reflexive for if p is an arbitrary element of $\mathbb{Z}_p$, we get $p \Delta C(p) = p \Delta C(p)$ for all $p \in \mathbb{Z}_p$. Hence $p \equiv p \Leftrightarrow p \Delta C(p) = p \Delta C(p) \quad \forall p \in \mathbb{Z}_p$.

ii) Symmetric, for if p and q are any elements of $\mathbb{Z}_p$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} p \equiv q, \text{ then } p \equiv q &\Leftrightarrow p \Delta C(p) = q \Delta C(q) \\ &\Leftrightarrow q \Delta C(q) = p \Delta C(p) \\ &\Leftrightarrow q \equiv p \end{aligned}$$

iii) transitive, for p, q, r are any three elements of $\mathbb{Z}_p$ such that

$$p \equiv q \text{ and } q \equiv r, \text{ then}$$

$$p \equiv q \Leftrightarrow p \Delta C(p) = q \Delta C(q) \text{ and}$$

$$q \equiv r \Leftrightarrow q \Delta C(q) = r \Delta C(r).$$

$$\text{Thus } p \Delta C(p) = r \Delta C(r) \Leftrightarrow p \equiv r$$

Hence $p \equiv q$ and $q \equiv r$ implies $p \equiv r$

6. D - Form of S. Gd.

Let $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$ be a S. Gd. of order m^n . Then the equivalence relation referred in the proposition 5.3 partitions $\mathbb{Z}_p$ into mutually disjoint classes.

Definition 6.1

If r be any element of S. Gd. $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$ such that $r \Delta C(r) = x$, then the equivalence class generated by x is denoted by Dx and defined by

$$Dx = \{ r \in \mathbb{Z}_p : r \Delta C(r) = x \}$$

The equivalence class generated by $\text{sup}(\mathbb{Z}_p)$ and defined by

$$D_{\text{sup}(\mathbb{Z}_p)} = \{ r \in \mathbb{Z}_p : r \Delta C(r) = \text{sup}(\mathbb{Z}_p) \} \text{ is called the D - form of } (\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta).$$

Example 6.2

Let $(\mathbb{Z}_9, +9)$ be a commutative group, then $\mathbb{Z}_9 = \{ 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 \}$. If the elements of $\mathbb{Z}_9$ are written as 3-adic numbers, then

$$\mathbb{Z}_9 = \{ (00)_3, (01)_3, (02)_3, (10)_3, (11)_3, (12)_3, (20)_3, (21)_3, (22)_3 \} \text{ and}$$

$(\mathbb{Z}_9, \Delta)$ is a S. Gd. of order $3^2 = 9$. Its composition table is as follows :

Δ	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
0	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	1	0	1	4	3	4	7	6	7
2	2	1	0	5	4	3	8	7	6
3	3	4	5	0	1	2	3	4	5
4	4	3	4	1	0	1	4	3	4
5	5	4	3	2	1	0	5	4	3
6	6	7	8	3	4	5	0	1	2
7	7	6	7	4	3	4	1	0	1
8	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0

Table - 3

Here $0 \Delta C(0) = 0 \Delta 8 = 8$
 $1 \Delta C(1) = 1 \Delta 7 = 6$
 $2 \Delta C(2) = 2 \Delta 6 = 8$
 $3 \Delta C(3) = 3 \Delta 5 = 2$
 $4 \Delta C(4) = 4 \Delta 4 = 0$
 $5 \Delta C(5) = 5 \Delta 3 = 2$
 $6 \Delta C(6) = 6 \Delta 2 = 8$
 $7 \Delta C(7) = 7 \Delta 1 = 6$
 $8 \Delta C(8) = 8 \Delta 0 = 8$

Hence $D_8 = \{ 0, 2, 6, 8 \} = \{(00)_3, (02)_3, (20)_3, (22)_3\}$
 $D_6 = \{ 1, 7 \}$
 $D_2 = \{ \bar{3}, \bar{5} \}$
 $D_0 = \{ 4 \}$

The self complement element of $(\mathbb{Z}_9, \Delta)$ is 4 and D- form of this S. Gd. is $\{0, 2, 6, 8\} = D_8$
 Here $\mathbb{Z}_9 = D_0 \cup D_2 \cup D_6 \cup D_8$.

Proposition 6.3

Any two equivalence classes in a S. Gd. $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$ are either disjoint or identical.

Proof is obvious.

Proposition 6.4

Every S. Gd. $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$ is equal to the union of its equivalence classes.

Proof is obvious.

Proposition 6.5

Every D- form of a S. Gd. $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$ is a commutative group.

Proof : Let $(\mathbb{Z}_p, \Delta)$ be a S. Gd. of order $P = m^n$. The elements of D- form of this groupoid are as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 &= (00 \dots \dots 00)_m \\
 m-1 &= (00 \dots \dots 0 \ m-1)_m \\
 m^2 - m &= (00 \dots \dots m-1 \ 0)_m \\
 m^2 - 1 &= (00 \dots \dots m-1 \ m-1)_m \\
 &\dots \dots \dots \dots \\
 &\dots \dots \dots \dots \\
 m^{n-1} - m &= (0 \ m-1 \dots \dots m-1 \ 0)_m \\
 m^{n-1} - 1 &= (0 \ m-1 \dots \dots m-1 \ m-1)_m \\
 m^n - m &= (m-1 \ m-1 \dots \dots m-1 \ 0)_m \\
 m^n - 1 &= (m-1 \ m-1 \dots \dots m-1 \ m-1)_m
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore D_{m^n-1} = \{ 0, m-1, m^2-m, m^2-1, \dots, m^{n-1}-m, m^{n-1}-1, m^n-m, m^n-1 \}$$

Here (D_{m^n-1}, Δ) is a commutative group and its table is given below :

Δ	0	$m-1$	m^2-m	m^2-1	...	$m^{n-1}-m$	$m^{n-1}-1$	m^n-m	m^n-1
0	0	$m-1$	m^2-m	m^2-1	...	$m^{n-1}-m$	$m^{n-1}-1$	m^n-m	m^n-1
$m-1$	$m-1$	0	m^2-1	m^2-m	...	$m^{n-1}-1$	$m^{n-1}-m$	m^n-1	m^n-m
m^2-m	m^2-m	m^2-1	0	$m-1$	...	m^n-m	m^n-1	$m^{n-1}-m$	$m^{n-1}-1$
m^2-1	m^2-1	m^2-m	$m-1$	0	...	m^n-1	m^n-m	$m^{n-1}-1$	$m^{n-1}-m$
---	---				...	---		---	
$m^{n-1}-m$	$m^{n-1}-m$	$m^{n-1}-1$	m^n-m	m^n-1	...	0	$m-1$	m^2-m	m^2-1
$m^{n-1}-1$	$m^{n-1}-1$	$m^{n-1}-m$	m^n-1	m^n-m	...	$m-1$	0	m^2-1	m^2-m
m^n-m	m^n-m	m^n-1	$m^{n-1}-m$	$m^{n-1}-1$	...	m^2-m	m^2-1	0	$m-1$
m^n-1	m^n-1	m^n-m	$m^{n-1}-1$	$m^{n-1}-m$	...	m^2-1	m^2-m	$m-1$	0

Table - 4

Remarks 6.6

Let $(\mathbf{Z}_p, \Delta)$ be a S. Gd. of order m^n .

The equivalence relation $p \cong q \Leftrightarrow p \Delta C(p) = q \Delta C(q)$ partitions $\mathbf{Z}_p$ into some equivalence classes.

i) If m is odd integer, then the number of elements belonging to the equivalence classes are not equal. In the example 6.2, the number of elements belonging to the equivalence classes D_0, D_2, D_6, D_8 are not equal due to $m = 3$.

ii) If m is even integer, then the number of elements belonging to the equivalence classes are equal.

For example, $\mathbf{Z}_{16} = \{ 0, 1, 2, \dots, 15 \}$ be a commutative group. If the elements of $\mathbf{Z}_{16}$ are expressed as 4- adic numbers, then $(\mathbf{Z}_{16}, \Delta)$ is a S. Gd. The composition table of $(\mathbf{Z}_{16}, \Delta)$ is given below :

Δ	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
0	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1	1	0	1	2	5	4	5	6	9	8	9	10	13	12	13	14
2	2	1	0	1	6	5	4	5	10	9	8	9	14	13	12	13
3	3	2	1	0	7	6	5	4	11	10	9	8	15	14	13	12
4	4	5	6	7	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
5	5	4	5	6	1	0	1	2	5	4	5	6	9	8	9	10
6	6	5	4	5	2	1	0	1	10	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
7	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	7	6	5	4	11	10	9	8
8	8	9	10	11	4	5	6	7	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
9	9	8	9	10	5	4	5	6	1	0	1	2	5	4	5	6
10	10	9	8	9	6	5	4	5	2	1	0	1	6	5	4	5
11	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	7	6	5	4
12	12	13	14	15	8	9	10	11	4	5	6	7	0	1	2	3
13	13	12	13	14	9	8	9	10	5	4	5	6	1	0	1	2
14	14	13	12	13	10	9	8	9	6	5	4	5	2	1	0	1
15	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0

Table - 5

Here $0 \Delta C(0) = 15 = 15 \Delta C(15)$

$1 \Delta C(1) = 13 = 14 \Delta C(14)$

$2 \Delta C(2) = 13 = 13 \Delta C(13)$

$3 \Delta C(3) = 15 = 12 \Delta C(12)$

$4 \Delta C(4) = 7 = 11 \Delta C(11)$

$5 \Delta C(5) = 5 = 10 \Delta C(10)$

$6 \Delta C(6) = 5 = 9 \Delta C(9)$

$7 \Delta C(7) = 7 = 8 \Delta C(8)$

Hence $D_{15} = \{ 0, 3, 12, 15 \}$, $D_{13} = \{ 1, 2, 13, 14 \}$

$D_7 = \{ 4, 8, 7, 11 \}$, $D_5 = \{ 5, 6, 9, 10 \}$

The number of elements of the equivalence classes are equal due to $m = 4$, which is even integer.

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